

HOW TO IMPROVE STUDENTS' READING COMPREHENSION THROUGH MATCHING HEADINGS IN THE CEFR TEST

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Annotation: CEFR Multilevel English exam includes various types of questions to assess students' cognitive skills. One of them is Matching Headings, it is to say that choosing an appropriate title for the paragraph. This kind of questions demand to understand the given text deeply, realize the original meaning thoroughly as well as conclude at a one point in a relatively short time span. This article explores the CEFR Multilevel English Test focusing on the MATCHING HEADING questions and help learners how to deal these ones appropriately and productively.

Key words; English Multilevel exam, importance of Matching Heading questions, understanding problems, methods to tackle.

Annotatsiya: CEFR ko'p bosqichli ingliz tili imtihoni talabalarning kognitiv qobiliyatlarini baholash uchun turli xil savollarni o'z ichiga oladi. Ulardan biri mos keladigan sarlavhalar bo'lib, bu paragraf uchun mos sarlavha tanlashdir. Bunday savollar berilgan matnni chuqur tushunishni, asl ma'nosini chuqur anglashni hamda nisbatan qisqa vaqt ichida bir nuqtada xulosa qilishni talab qiladi. Ushbu maqola MATCHING HEADING savollariga qaratilgan CEFR Multi Level English Testini o'rganadi va o'quvchilarga bu savollarni to'g'ri va samarali hal qilishda yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar; Ingliz tilidan ko'p darajali imtihon, mos keladigan sarlavha savollarining ahamiyati, muammolarni tushunish, hal qilish usullari.

Аннотация: Экзамен CEFR Multilevel English включает в себя различные типы вопросов для оценки когнитивных навыков студентов. Один из них — это вопросы Matching Headings, то есть выбор подходящего заголовка для абзаца. Этот тип вопросов требует глубокого понимания данного текста, полного понимания исходного смысла, а также заключения в одной точке за относительно короткий промежуток времени. В этой статье рассматривается тест CEFR Multilevel English, фокусирующийся на вопросах MATCHING HEADING

и помогающий учащимся решать их правильно и продуктивно. **Ключевые слова;** экзамен English Multilevel, важность вопросов Matching Heading, проблемы понимания, методы решения.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 The CEFR [Common European Framework of Reference for Languages] test is an internationally recognized system for assessing language proficiency levels, offering several advantages for students and language learners. These days, the number of applicants who apply for Multilevel exam has been rising day by day because of its affordable price and comfortability. People can get different degrees according to their knowledge level as well as may apply for universities or works with B2 level. It emerges much more convenience and easiness for people. The CEFR test evaluates students from A1 to C2 levels, providing a precise measurement of their language skills. This helps learners identify their current level and plan their future language learning process effectively.

1.2 Matching Heading questions persuade candidates to think critically, quickly and correctly. Because there are more options than paragraphs which have almost the same meaning with the correct answer, by means of these questions examiners check students' logical thinking, English understanding and how they work with this type of matters.

1.3 Questions help students identify and grasp the main ideas of the text, encouraging them to go beyond superficial reading to gain a deeper understanding. Analytical questions enhance students' logical thinking skills, helping them identify cause-and-effect relationships, distinguish primary and secondary information, and evaluate the structure of the text. Answering questions teaches to approach the text critically, enabling them to evaluate its content and form their own opinions about the author's ideas and arguments.

Challenges Candidates Face in Solving Matching Headings Questions

1. General challenges.

1. *Focusing too much on details.* Some candidates try to read every word in the paragraph, which wastes valuable time.
2. *Misunderstanding keywords.* They fail to recognize synonyms or contextual meanings, leading to incorrect answers.
3. *Inability to identify the main idea.* Candidates struggle to grasp the overall theme of the paragraph, causing confusion.

4. *Difficulty with similar headings.* When headings are similar, it becomes harder to select the most accurate one.
5. *Poor time management.* Matching Headings questions can take up a lot of time if approached ineffectively.

Here some effective tips for solving matching heading tasks;

Skim the text first

Skimming is one of the tools you have to use to read more in less time. It is strategic, selective method which test-takers quickly read through the text to get a general understanding of the main idea and focus on the overall meaning of the paragraph rather than specific details. Skimming may present problems if not done intentionally. It is not simply flipping through a text quickly or paying half attention to it. When skimming, be deliberate and intentional with what you choose to read, and make sure that you are focused. Skimming is not a lazy way out or a half-hearted attempt at reading. Make sure that you use it carefully and strategically and are able to walk away with the main ideas of the text.

Watch for signal words and phrases that indicate an author's direction. Things to focus on while skimming;

Introduction and conclusion

Chapter/section summaries

First and last sentences

Titles, subtitles, and headings

Bold words

Italics

Charts, graphs, or pictures

End of chapter review questions

These indicators help to candidates to save their times and find the best headings for the paragraphs.

Scanning

Scanning a text means looking through it quickly to find specific information. Scanning is commonly used in everyday life, for example when looking up a word in a dictionary or finding your friend's name in the contacts directory of your phone. Scanning and another quick reading skill, **skimming**, are often confused, though they are quite different. While skimming is concerned with finding *general information* namely the main ideas, scanning involves looking for *specific information*.

Before you start scanning for information, you should try to understand how the text is arranged. This will help you to locate the information more quickly. For example, when

scanning for a word in a dictionary or friend's name in your contact list, you already know that the information is arranged alphabetically. This means you can go more quickly to the part you want, without having to look through everything. For this reason, skimming can be a useful skill to use in combination with scanning, to give you a general idea of the text structure. Section headings, if there are any, can be especially useful. When scanning, you will be looking for key words or phrases. These will be especially easy to find if they are names, because they will begin with a capital letter, or numbers/dates. Once you have decided on the area of the text to scan, you should run your eyes down the page, to take in as much of the text as possible. This approach makes scanning seem much more random than other speed reading skills such as skimming and surveying. It is also a good idea to use your finger as you move down [or back up] the page, to focus your attention and keep track of where you are.

Keywords Matching

Keywords matching is an effective method to solve **Matching Headings** questions in the Reading section. It helps you to identify the connection between the heading and the paragraph by focusing on key words and phrases. Here's a detailed explanation of this method;

1. What are Keywords

Keywords are:

- **Nouns, verbs, adjectives;** Words that convey the main idea
- **Numbers, dates, names, places;** specific details in the text
- Synonyms or variations of a word are often used as well.

Example;

Heading; *The impact of technology on education*

Keywords; *technology, impact, education.*

2. Steps for Keywords Matching

Step 1. Read and analyze the headings.

- Identify the main keywords in each heading.
- Think of possible synonyms. For example;

impact = effect

technology = digital tools, devices.

Step 2. Scan the text.

- Search the text for the keywords or their synonyms.
- Keywords are often found at the beginning or the end of a paragraph.

Step 3. Analyze the context.

- Once you locate the keywords, read the sentences around them.

- Ensure that the meaning of the paragraph matches the heading.

3. Tips for Identifying Keywords

1. Focus on synonyms

- In text and headings, synonyms are often used instead of exact words.
- Example; *Global warming* in the heading might be written as *climate change* in the text.

2. Pay attention to specific sentences

- Keywords are frequently found in the topic sentence or concluding sentence of a paragraph.

3. Avoid generic words

- Focus on words that highlight the main idea rather than filler words.

Example Practice

Heading;

The importance of physical activity for children.

Keywords; physical activity, children, importance/

Text; [Paragraph]

Engaging in sports helps children develop physically and mentally. Regular exercises, such as running, swimming, or team sports, contribute to their overall health and well-being.

- Keywords in the text match with the heading; *physical activity* = sports, regular exercises, *children* = children, *importance* = health and well-being.

The heading matches the paragraph.

4. Mistakes to avoid

1. **Do not rely solely on keywords**; Sometimes the keywords match, but the context does not. Always analyze the meaning.

2. **Focus on relevance, not similarity**; Ensure that the heading and the paragraph are directly related in meaning, not just in words.

4. Elimination

This method helps you focus only on relevant headings, saves time with removing unrelated headings, you narrow down your options quickly and improves accuracy by minimizing the chances of selecting distractor heading. Let's do it together;

Technology has revolutionized communication, making it faster and more accessible. Innovations such as video calls and instant messaging have replaced traditional methods like letters. These advancements have connected people worldwide and changed how we interact.

Headings;

1. The role of technology in education.
2. The evolution of global communication
3. The negative impacts of modern technology
4. Traditional communication methods

Eliminating process

Heading 1; mentions education, which is not discussed in the paragraph. ELIMINATE
Heading 3; talks about negative impacts, but the paragraph emphasizes positive changes. ELIMINATE

Heading 4; Focuses on traditional traditional communication, but the paragraph mainly discusses innovations. ELIMINATE

Heading 2; matches the paragraph's main idea about how communication has evolved globally. CORRECT ANSWER

By practicing this method, you can solve Matching Heading questions with greater confidence and efficiency.

5. Contextual Understanding

Contextual understanding refers to the ability to comprehend and interpret information in relation to the surrounding environment or situation, enabling meaningful interpretation beyond just the literal words or data presented. This skill is fundamental for effective communication, as it allows individuals to grasp nuances, social cues, and implied meanings, thereby facilitating better interpersonal relationships and decision-making. By improving contextual understanding, students can enhance their critical thinking and analytical skills which are really in demand in Reading section. While working with Matching Headings you should be careful with the method you use, because as you know, time is limited and candidates ought to utilize only productive methods. Contextual Understanding encourages distinguish main ideas from supporting details, ensures the heading reflects the central idea, not minor details. It enhances logical flow; understand how the paragraph fits into the overall structure of the passage.

6. Analytical Thinking

1. ***Identify the main idea;*** analyze why the information is presented in the paragraph. Focus on understanding the core message rather than specific details.
2. ***Examine Connections;*** Study how the information in the paragraph relates to the overall passage. This helps in determining the heading that best represents the content.
3. ***Compare and Contrast Options;*** Carefully evaluate each heading option and decide which one aligns most closely with the main idea of the paragraph.

Paragraph

Many people believe that multitasking improves productivity, but research suggests otherwise. Studies show that switching between tasks can lead to a loss of focus and lower efficiency. Instead, focusing on one task at a time allows individuals to achieve better results. This method, often referred to as „single-tasking’’, has been proven to enhance concentration and overall performance.

Heading Options;

- 1. Benefits of multitasking**
- 2. Why multitasking reduces productivity**
- 3. Tips for improving focus**
- 4. Single-tasking vs Multitasking**

Analytical Thinking in Action;

1. Identify the main idea

- The paragraph discusses how the multitasking is not productive and emphasizes the benefits of single-tasking.

2. Examine connections

- The research presented focus on the disadvantages of multitasking and highlights single-tasking as a better alternative.

3. Compare and contrast options

Option 1. Mentions the benefits of multitasking, but the paragraph discusses its disadvantages.

Option 3. Mentions tips for focus, but the paragraph does not provide actionable tips – it explains research findings.

Option 4 seems relevant but is not the core focus; it only mentions single-tasking in the conclusions.

Option 2 is the best fit, as the paragraph primarily discusses why multitasking reduces productivity.

Correct Heading is second one. „ Why Multitasking reduces productivity’’

Reading sections demand us to be intelligent, for improving our reading comprehension we have to read thought-provoking books, solve puzzles and brain teasers, practice debating and reasoning, take online courses like Udemy, Khan Academy or Coursera, write an analyze to topics, learn programming and math deeply, engage in strategic games like chess, strategy-based video games encourage planning and logical reasoning and of course, challenge assumptions. Practice asking WHY and WHAT IF to deepen your understanding. While doing these and above tips you can

develop your outlook, horizon as well as critical thinking and as a result you have a potential perception to the reading task.

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